

SKILL ASSESSMENT OF HOSPITALITY PROFESSIONALS: STUDY OF EMPLOYEES WORKING IN BUDGET CATEGORY HOTELS IN VIDARBHA REGION

S.R. Kapse and R.J. Thomas

Department of Travel & Tourism Studies, Vishwakarma University, Pune, M.S

ABSTRACT

Making use of the available human resources and skills is a formidable task. Qualified employees are always productive and become the backbone of the hospitality and tourism industry if managed and used properly from the bottom level. Job satisfaction is one of the important criteria to respond to the dynamic and increasing challenges of the service sector, especially budget hotels. This study is an attempt to assess the competence of Budget Hotel employees working in the Vidarbha area based on age, gender and education along with the tasks assigned to them in certain departments, such as cleaning, food and food production.

The sample consisted of 100 employees from 20 different budget hotels in the Vidarbha region and around its popular tourist destinations. An extensive literature review was conducted on the basis of qualitative data. Skills of employees give importance to certain factors such as skills that are appropriate to their age, gender and education along with reward systems, opportunities for promotion and career advancement and other structures etc. This can increase employee productivity and satisfaction for Budget Hotel Employees working in the Vidarbha area.

Keywords: Skill Assessment, Budget Hotels, Employee Satisfaction, Hospitality, Nagpur

Introduction

Tourism and hospitality is the largest and fastest growing industry globally (Walker, 2010). The growth of tourism has influenced the development of the hospitality industry. The hospitality industry is becoming increasingly demanding in terms of service quality which affects the success of hotels. The quality of service depends on the quality of the hotel employees. Employee quality is related to knowledge, skills, competence, experience, etc. (Gazija, 2012). The Indian hospitality industry has emerged as a key industry driving the growth of the service sector and, by extension, the nation's economy. However, the Indian hotel industry is confronted with numerous factors imposed by a rapidly changing external environment. As a result of the intense competition, many hotels have been forced to improve service quality, guest satisfaction, and hotel performance in order to remain competitive. 2010 (Chand)

Maharashtra is a state of India in the western region of the country and is India's third largest state, with a coastline of 720 kms. It also offers a variety of tourist products ranging from the Western Ghats, the Sahyadri mountain range, hill stations, water reservoirs with semi-evergreen forests, to several wild life sanctuaries, and nature parks, among others (maharashtratourism.gov.in, Maharashtra

unlimited magazine). With the availability of infrastructure and the variety of tourist themes offered by numerous destinations, Maharashtra's tourism industry has enormous growth potential (Dr. Joshi 2014).

Vidarbha especially Nagpur is the second capital for the state of Maharashtra also known as the Tiger capital of India. It is the regional headquarter of Vidarbha Region, with a huge variety of tourist products ranging from wildlife sanctuaries, heritage sites, and destinations with cultural and religious importance, hence it attracts millions of domestic tourists making tourism one of the integral parts of the local economy.

Review of Literature

World Tourism Organization (UNWTO, 2010), youth travel accounted for 20 percent of international tourists in 2010. Their trips are projected to reach nearly 300 million by 2020. Therefore, there is a direct result of the growth of the Budget hotel market as young travelers usually prefer to stay in economy class. Therefore, to meet the needs of guests/tourists, it is very important for a hotel to have qualified and professional employees in order to provide the highest standard of service. The requirement for skilled workers in the hotel sector is a demand for international tourism (Expert Group on Future Skills, 2015). By

2022, it plans to train 4.5cr people with employable skills as part of the Indian government's strategic development plan. (NSD, 2013). It should be noted that since 1996 the main infrastructure investment in India has been in the hospitality sector, compared to other sectors (Devendra A, 2001). For this reason there has been a significant development in the hotel chain business and all chains (Lahari A, et.al, 2000). The Indian hospitality industry has developed as one of the vital service industries to support the Indian economy. (FHRAI, 2015-16).

Budget hotels are a new idea in providing hospitality to guests (Fiorentino, 1995 & Ruetz and Marvel 2011) defining budget hotels as transitional accommodations that apply low rates. Such hotels usually have a standard "cookiecutter" look and feel and offer a systematic and no-nonsense format of service, e.g. G. Limited food and beverage and meeting facilities. Similarly Quest 1983 defines budget hotels as 'a new generation of budget hotels, mostly small and all with limited facilities and no-frills prices'. According to Lee 11 1984 research, a budget hotel is one of the 'fastest-growing segments of the industry,' offering 'clean, simple rooms, a restaurant coffee shop is generally on-site nearby.' However, Rahimi and Kozak (2016) stated that the terms "budget hotel," "limited service hotel," and "economy hotel" are used interchangeably throughout the hospitality industry, with no standardization of operations.

Vidarbha & Marathwada's tourism potential is underutilized due to poor connectivity and service quality (Pandagale 2014). Service quality is regarded as the lifeblood of any hotel; it is assessed as an important core aspect and a critical success factor in hotels. Al-Ababneh (2017) as a result, the hospitality industry has seen intense competition for high service quality and customer satisfaction (Sharma 2007). According to Parasuraman et al. (1988), service quality can be defined as an overall judgement that is similar to the attitude toward the service and is widely accepted as a predictor of overall customer satisfaction (Zeithaml and Bitner, 1996). According to Parasuraman et al. (1988), service quality is defined as an organization's ability to meet or exceed customer expectations. It is the

difference between what customers expect and what they actually receive (Zeithaml et al., 1990).

The guest (customer) recognizing the difference in service quality could be due to a variety of factors such as skill levels, consumer perception, participation behaviour, service providers' personality, motivation, and so on. 2004 (Luk and Layton) Employee skills studies that have been included According to Acharya and Siddiq (2016), the success of the hospitality industry is dependent on its human resources. Employee effectiveness is achieved by providing the appropriate skills at the appropriate times while providing service. However, the qualities of an employee working in the hotel industry are most closely related to skills, knowledge, experience, competences, and so on, all of which contribute to the development of the hotels. According to Riley et al. (2002), "skills are constantly surrounded by controversy because perceptions of skills are highly subjective and relative." (Gazija, 2011) Green (2011) defines skill as one of those social science words in common parlance with multiple meanings, numerous synonyms such as "ability," "competence," "knack," "aptitude," and "talent," and various imprecise translations in other languages. Skills are a person's ability/capabilities to perform a specific set of tasks that are developed through training and experience (Blanchard and Thacker, 1999; Gronroos, 2000).

Statement of the Problem

Within the global agendas and modern development trends, the hospitality industry represents an important profession (Pavia et al., 2014). BAUM 2002 stated that skills in services are a core segment of the hospitality industry, more than in any other industry, and that employees in the hospitality industry must have developed skills in all essential areas of management. Similarly, Ragde 2019 stated on World Tourism Day Celebration that a large workforce is globally employed in tourism and hospitality, but they face challenges in matching its skill requirements to cater to the needs of the guests. According to Jogdand (2017), the Indian tourism sector confronts various challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, visitor safety and security, a lack

of marketing tactics, and a shortage of competent labour.

The Indian hotel sector has a high attrition rate (Kashyap, 2014). To manage the hotel industry from the bartender to the top management level, appropriate specialists are required (Rathore 2012). (Whitelaw, et.al.) Because of this at high-level jobs, it is difficult to recruit people with the right skills and flexibility, commitment and presentation. In addition, research by Baum and Devine (2005) addresses several issues in the hospitality and tourism industry, in particular with the shortage of skilled workers, which limits the growth potential of the industry. The hospitality industry also faces a number of problems that need to be resolved quickly, such as: low quality and skills of employees and low level of training (Siddiq 2016) As a result, the hospitality industry has seen increasing competition for high quality of service and, ultimately, highly skilled and skilled employees. This created a significant research gap. Therefore, the researcher examined the skills of employees working in budget hotels in the Vidarbha area.

Objective

1. To evaluate the skills of employees working in the budget hotels in Vidarbha Region.

Hypothesis

1. The employees in the budget hotels of Maharashtra lack skills.

Methodology

The aim of the study is to assess the skills of employees working in budget hotels in the Vidarbha region through self-assessment. The staff of budget hotels in the Vidarbha area are believed to lack skills. The study comprises a collection of primary and secondary data, the collection of primary data is carried out through a survey of 100 employees of 20 different budget hotels in the Vidarbha region and in the vicinity of its famous tourist destination. The primary data was collected through a survey of 160 employees in 20 budget hotels in the Vidarbha region (Maharashtra) and near its famous tourist destination. After extensive bibliographic research, a questionnaire was developed based on a 33-point scale of the essential skills required in the four main departments of a hotel (Reception, Cleaning, Food and Beverage, and Food Production). Subsequently, the employees were given questionnaires for self-assessment of their capabilities on a 5-point Likert scale with “1” for “very satisfactory” and “5” for “very unsatisfactory”. Sampling methods were used in the selection of hotels and employees.

Data Analysis: H0: Gender, Age and Education of the employees and their skills are not significantly correlated. i.e. r is equals to zero.

H1: Gender, Age and Education of the employees and their skills is significantly correlated. i.e. r is not equals to zero.

Spearman's Rank Correlations

	Gender	Communication Skill	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Q12	Q13
Gender	1	0.022	0.135	-0.003	-0.009	0.107	0.025	0.04	0.087	0.093	0.127	-0.024	-0.059	0.025
	p-value	0.778	0.082	0.972	0.909	0.107	0.746	0.605	0.267	0.236	0.104	0.763	0.448	0.753
	Age	Speaking Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Q12	Q13
Age	1	-0.004	-0.114	-0.032	-0.018	0.022	-0.008	-0.016	-0.002	-0.099	-0.005	0.066	0.051	0.039
	p-value	0.961	0.144	0.679	0.822	0.775	0.305	0.836	0.982	0.204	0.95	0.399	0.511	0.613
	Education	Speaking Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Q12	Q13
Education	1	0.048	0.071	.196*	0.11	0.058	.167*	-0.07	-0.02	0.094	-0.02	.178*	0.095	0.006

								7	9		3			
p-value	P-value	0.538	0.36 2	0.01 1	0.15 7	0.4 58	0.0 32	0.32 4	0.70 8	0.22 8	0.76 5	0.02 2	0.22 4	0.4 45

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the previous correlation matrix, in each case by gender and employee skills, p-value is greater than the significance level. Therefore, accept the null hypothesis. From this we conclude that the gender of the employees and their skills are not significantly correlated i.e. its correlation is zero.

If we also verify the correlation between oral competence and other skills, they are significantly correlated since their p-value is below the 5% (0.05) level of significance. And so on.

In any case, for the age and skills of the employees, the p-value is greater than the significance level. Therefore, accept the null hypothesis. From this we conclude that the age of the employees and their abilities are not significantly correlated i.e. its correlation is zero.

Furthermore, if we verify the correlation between oral competence and other skills, they are significantly correlated because their p-value is below the 5% (0.05) level of significance. And so on.

The p-value is also greater than the significance level for employee training and skills. Therefore, accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude that employee education and skills are not significantly correlated. i.e., their correlation is zero. Except in the case of teaching and writing skills, grooming, accounting skills are significantly correlated. Because the p-value is less than the 5% significance level (0.05). In addition, when we control the correlation between oral skills and other skills, they are significantly correlated because their p-value is lower than the significance level of 5% (0.05). etc.

House Keeping

	Gender	Q14	Q15	Q16	Q17	Q18	Q19	Q20
Gender	1	-0.029	0.069	0.093	0.029	0.037	-0.004	0.003
	p-value	0.733	0.422	0.282	0.734	0.67	0.961	0.969
	Age	Q14	Q15	Q16	Q17	Q18	Q19	Q20
Age	1	-0.13	-0.153	-0.141	-.228**	-0.105	-.240**	-.214*
	p-value	0.13	0.075	0.1	0.007	0.224	0.005	0.012
	Education	Q14	Q15	Q16	Q17	Q18	Q19	Q20
Education	1	0.069	0.145	0.142	0.033	0.078	-0.014	.197*
	p-value	0.42	0.091	0.098	0.698	0.365	0.871	0.021

From the above correlation matrix, for each of the employee's gender and skills, the p-value is greater than the significance level. So let's accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude that the gender of employees and their skills are not significantly correlated i.e. their correlation is zero.

For each of the employees' ages and skills, the p-value is greater than the significance level. So let's accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude that the gender of employees and their skills are not significantly correlated i.e. their correlation is zero.

In addition to age and room making skills, room maintenance, room inventory, and laundry care skills are significantly correlated. Because the p-value is less than the 5% significance level (0.05). For all employee training and skills, the p-value is greater than the significance level. So let's accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude that employee education and skills are not significantly correlated. i.e., their correlation is zero.

Except in the case of education and room inventory, laundry care skills are significantly correlated. Because the p-value is lower than the 5% significance level (0.05).

Food Production Spearman's Rank Correlations

	Gender	Q21	Q22	Q23	Q24	Q25	Q26
Gender
	p-value
	Age	Q21	Q22	Q23	Q24	Q25	Q26
Age	1	-0.029	-0.036	0.033	-0.07	-0.036	-0.065
	p-value	0.78	0.729	0.751	0.503	0.727	0.532
	Education	Q21	Q22	Q23	Q24	Q25	Q26
Education	1	-0.048	-0.019	0.163	0.039	0.02	-0.133
	p-value	0.647	0.855	0.114	0.707	0.848	0.2

All respondents are male, so this does not correlate. According to the above correlation matrix, for each of the employee's age and skills, the p-value is greater than the significance level. So let's accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude that the age of employees and their skills are not

significantly correlated. i.e. their correlation is zero.

For all employee training and skills, the p-value is greater than the significance level. So let's accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude that employee education and skills are not significantly correlated. i.e., their correlation is zero.

Food and Beverage

	Gender	Q27	Q28	Q29	Q30	Q31	Q32	Q33
Gender	1	0.182	0.049	0.191	0.134	0.116	.196*	.205*
	p-value	0.068	0.627	0.055	0.179	0.244	0.048	0.039
	Age	Q27	Q28	Q29	Q30	Q31	Q32	Q33
Age	1	-0.09	-0.038	-0.135	-0.084	-0.119	-0.12	-0.017
	p-value	0.371	0.701	0.175	0.399	0.234	0.23	0.869
	Edu	Q27	Q28	Q29	Q30	Q31	Q32	Q33
Edu	1	0.087	0.132	0.15	0.179	0.187	.331**	.317**
	p-value	0.387	0.187	0.133	0.071	0.06	0.001	0.001

From the correlation matrix mentioned above, in any case, the gender and skill of the employee, the p-value is greater than the significance level. Then accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude that the gender of employees and their skills are not significantly correlated i.e. the correlation is zero.

Except in terms of gender and the ability to minimize complaints, the ability to ensure the functioning of catering skills is significantly correlated. Because the p-value is below the 5% (0.05) significance level.

In terms of age and skills of employees, the value is greater than the level of significance. Then accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude that employees' age and their skills are not significantly correlated i.e. the correlation is zero.

In each case of employee education and skills, the p-value is greater than the significance level. Then accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude that employees' education and their skills are not significantly correlated i.e. the correlation is zero. Except for education and the ability to minimize complaints, the ability to ensure the smooth functioning of the catering capacity is significantly correlated. Because the p-value is below the 5% (0.05) significance level.

Conclusion & Suggestions

Today, India's hospitality and tourism industry is facing a mismatch between supply and demand as the economy requires more "skilled" human resources. In fact, most budget hotels remain virtually disconnected from the demands of the workplace. It can be seen that the skills of the employees do not match their age, gender and education. These factors can

turn out to be productive and less productive depending on proper implementation. To increase employee morale, work performance with productivity and satisfaction, strategic management support is needed in the workplace, which results in high profits, customer and employee loyalty.

While producing quality human resources, the education system must integrate the requirements of the hospitality and tourism industry into its schemes and curricula with an innovative and flexible approach. However, it

is necessary to take a concerted initiative to acquire knowledge and update skills of skilled employees directly from lower levels. For this, the initiatives of the Industrial Academy must be aligned. This skill mechanism is sure to change the current human resource landscape in the country's budget hotels. Implementing proper skill acquisition will facilitate employees to acquire adequate knowledge and training to get suitable jobs or even become entrepreneurs.

References

1. Acharya, G. and Siddiq, A. (2016). "Hospitality Skill Survey – an Empirical study of Star Hotel Employees skill Requirements in D K District of Karnataka", Conference: Business education and employability: challenges and new directions, volume 01. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321728623>
2. Al-Ababneh MM. (2017) "Service Quality in the Hospitality Industry", *Journal of Tourism and Hospitality* 6: e133. doi: 10.4172/2167-0269.1000e133.
3. BAUM, T. (2002), "Skills and training for the hospitality sector: a review of issues", *Journal of Vocational Education & Training* 54:3, 343-364, DOI: 10.1080/13636820200200204.
4. Baum, T. and Devine. F. (2005), "Skills and training in the hotel sector: The case of front office employment in Northern Ireland", *International Tourism and Hospitality Management*, Volume: 7 issue: 3-4, page(s): 269-280.
5. Blanchard N and Thacker J. (1999), "Effective Training: system, strategies and practices", Prentice hall, ISBN: 0132681609, 9780132681605.
6. Chand, M. (2010). The impact of HRM practices on service quality, customer satisfaction and performance in the Indian hotel industry, *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 21:4, 551-566, DOI: 10.1080/09585191003612059
7. Devendra, Amitabh (2001) "The Hotel Industry in India-The Past and the Present," *Journal of Hospitality Financial Management: Vol. 9: Iss. 1, Article 7.*
8. Expert group on future skills, (2015). Assessment of future skills required in hospitality sector in Ireland, 2015-2020.
9. Fiorentino A (1995) Budget hotels: not just minor hospitality products, *Tourism Management*, Vol. 16, No. 6, pp. 455-462.
10. Gazija A (2011), Importance of staff training in hotel industry Case Study: Hotel Dukagjini, *Iilria International Review – 2011/2.*
11. Gazija, A. (2011). Importance of staff training in hotel industry Case Study: Hotel Dukagjini, volume 01 ILIRAI international review.
12. Green F. (2011). "What is Skill? An Inter-Disciplinary Synthesis", Centre for learning life chances in knowledge economies and societies, ISSN: 20425929.
13. Gronroos, C. (2000) "Service management and marketing: A customer relationship management approach", Wiley, ISBN: 0471720348, 9780471720348.
14. http://cf.cdn.unwto.org/sites/all/files/pdf/amreports_vol2_thepowerofyouthtourism_eng_lw.pdf
15. <https://www.maharashtratourism.gov.in/>
16. Jogdand, B, (2017), "A Study of the Importance Performance Analysis of CSR Activities of Hotel Industry in Aurangabad", *Contemporary Tourism Planning, Introspecting Problems and Prospects(pp.206-214)Excel India Pvt Ltd.* ISBN :978-93-82880-57-8

17. Joshi, V. M. (2014). Development and marketing of tourism in Maharashtra, *International Journal of Management & Business Studies*, 4(21), 2230–9519.
18. Kashyap G (2014), Challenges faced by the Hotel Industry: a review of Indian Scenario, *Journal of Business and Management*, Volume 16, Issue 9.
19. Lahari, A. et.al, (2000). A Study of Tariffs in Indian Hotels, National institute of public finance and policy 18/2, satsang vihar marg, New Delhi.
20. Lee, D R '1: An introduction" in "The budgets: three views" Cornell H R A Quarterly 1984 (May).
21. Luk. S and Layton R. (2004), "Managing both outcome process quality is critical to quality of hotel service", *Total quality management and business excellence*, vol.15, issue 3, pp.289-278
22. Maharashtra Unlimited Magazine Vol 05, issue 03.
23. Pandagale, P. (2014) "Geospatial Technology for Tourism Management in Vidarbha City", *International Journal of Computer Applications* (0975 – 8887) Volume 102– No.16.
24. Parasuraman et al. (1988) SERVQUAL: A multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perception of service quality. *Journal of Retailing* 64: 12-40.
25. Parasuraman, Berry and Zeithaml (1990) "An Empirical Examination of Relationships in an Extended Service Quality Model", *Marketing Science Institute Research Program Series*, 12, 90-122.
26. Pavia, N. et al., (2014), "Specialisation As A Trend In Modern Hotel Industry", 22nd Biennial International Congress Tourism & Hospitality Industry,.
27. Quest, M 'Is there a future for low-tariff UK hotels?' *Caterer & Hotelkeeper* 1983 (29 September) 55-61.
28. Ragde, R. (2019), "World Tourism Day Event", 27th September 2019 at Department of Tourism Administration, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University.
29. Rahimi R & Kozak M (2016), "Impact of customer relationship management on customer satisfaction: the case study of a budget hotel chain", *Journal of travel and tourism management*. doi: 10.1080/10548408.2015.1130108.
30. Rathore, N. (2012), "A study on mapping of human resource skill gap in tourism industry", *International Journal of Marketing, Financial Services and Management Research* Vol.01 No. 2
31. Riley, M. et.al. (2002), "Tourism Employment", Channel View Publications, UK, p. 99.
32. Ruetz D and Marvel M. (2011), "Budget hotels: low cost concepts in the U.S., Europe and Asia" trends and issues in global tourism pp.99-124.
33. Sawant, M. (2017). Socio – Economic Impact of Tourism Development at Vidarbha District, In Dias F.(Eds.), *A pathway for the new generation of tourism research-Proceedings of EATSA*. Portugal. ISBN: 978-989-20-7217-3.
34. Sharma, C (2014) A Service Quality Model Applied on Indian Hotel Industry to Measure the Level of Customer Satisfaction *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)* ISSN (Online): 2319-7064.
35. UNWTO report on Power of youth Travelers, Retrieved from
36. Walker, J. (2010), *Introduction to Hospitality Management*, Pearson Education, London ISBN-13:9780135061381.
37. Whitelaw, P. et.al, (2014), "Training needs of the hospitality industry", *CRC for Sustainable Tourism*, ISBN: 9781921658105 (pbk.) 9781921658600 (pdf.).
38. Zeithaml V. and Bitner M. (1996) "Services Marketing", McGraw Hill, ISBN: 0070782504, 9780070782501.